

Traditional Concept Change in Digital Libraries Effect on Users at Panskura Banamali College Central Library: A Case Study

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Abstract

Digital library is a rather new concept in higher education at Panskura Banamali College, is a (State) Govt. aided college affiliated to Vidyasagar University. This was accredited with grade "A" by NAAC in 2005 and reaccredited with "A" Grade in 2016, arguably the largest college in Rural Bengal, in terms of its strength of students and the number of subjects taught at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels. Recently, UGC has elevated the status to a Ph.D. Degree College. library with OPAC system and internet facilities for students. The college has to function in three shifts: Day Section, Morning Section (Extended Day) and Evening Section. The Central library of this college Digitization at 2013, Manual library user affected on Digitization, Searching has become fast on a digital library as compared to a traditional library.

Keywords: Trends of academic library under digital India Programme, Benefit of digitization, Rural Students trends use of library.

Introduction

Digital library The term was first popularized by the NASA Digital Libraries Initiative in 1994. The digital library concept is not a single entity. Library bibliographic networks are among the first governmental online services provided in many communities and higher educational institutes. To make e-government effective, governmental agencies have learned an important lesson of management and technology issues (authenticity, security, interoperability, etc.) through online library services, which made them an important team player. A traditional library is characterized by the following: emphasis on storage and preservation of physical items, particularly books and periodicals cataloguing at a high level rather than one of detail,

Different between traditional and digital libraries is below.

Traditional Libraries	Digital or Electronic Library
Print collection	All resources in digital form.
Stable, with slow evolution	Dynamic and ephemeral
Individual objects not directly linked with each other.	Multi-media and fractal objects
The physical and logical organization correlated.	The physical and logical organization may be virtually
One way interactions	Dynamic real time dialogue
Free and universal access.	Free as well as fee based.

A traditional library is characterized by the following:

1. Cataloguing at a high level rather than one of detail, e.g., author and subject indexes as opposed to full text
2. Cataloguing down to individual words or glyphs

Once one is comfortable with sizes of this kind, it is feasible to imagine a thousand such databases, or to envision them all apportions of the same global collection.

1. Photographs
2. Legislative material, court decisions
3. Museum objects
4. Recorded music
5. Theatrical performances, including opera and ballet

6. Speeches
7. Movies and videotape

Function of Digital Library

1. Access to large amounts of information to users wherever they are and whenever they need it.
2. Access to primary information sources.
3. Support multimedia content along with text
4. Network accessibility on Intranet and Internet
5. User-friendly interface
6. Hypertext links for navigation
7. Client-server architecture
8. Advanced search and retrieval.
9. Integration with other digital libraries.
10. It is easier and more convenient to use.

Objective of the Paper

Digital or Electronic Library is a rather new concept in higher education at Panskura Banamali College in rural Bengal, only being used since 2013, allowing researchers and students to access information electronically in various subjects. As this is a new service for students and library staff, they are still learning to access and search useful information from it. Students get no help while searching content from their laptop in college or computer labs, but only if they go to the Panskura Banamali College library to seek help. But it is difficult to decide the usefulness of any of the two libraries for higher education students as very little work has been done on this topic in rural Bengal at Panskura Banamali College. Digital or Electronic Library being online. This has given us a clear picture of the scenario, which has further helped us to improve the situation for students during their research and education by giving them better service. This study was conducted in rural Bengal to explore the role of libraries in higher education from a student's perspective.

Review of Literature

After evolution of new technologies such as internet and World Wide Web (WWW), which provides technological environment for development of Digital

or Electronic Library, it contains less date and more ideas. The main reason to establish a Digital or Electronic Library is to provide better and the latest information to users, which is not possible in the past. Digital or Electronic Library has no limits. There is no need of physical place or items. Some of these registration-only works are from sources such as:

1. World eBook Library
2. South Asia Archive
3. OECD iLibrary
4. Satyajit Ray Society

The programme was funded by the MHRD under NME-ICT to extend access to selected e-resources to colleges covered under Section 12B of UGC Act as well as Non-aided colleges during from 2010 - 2013. Panskura Banamali College central library is a member of this framework to provide degree awarding institutes.

Conceptual Framework

There is no specific model available to compare both libraries, the fundamental functions of libraries, which are

1. Purchasing or acquiring books, journals, etc.
2. Searching a specific book when a library has Thousands of books
3. Delivery of information.

To check the performance of any library for its usefulness, these are basic functions which can give true reflection of reality of any library and its contribution towards its user.

1. Access location
2. Interaction
3. Search
4. Query of access.

All these functions are essential for any library and it covers all aspects of traditional and Digital or Electronic Library so this is one of the reasons to choose this framework.

Comparison of Traditional Manual Library and Digital or Electronic Library

Attributes	Traditional Manual Library	Digital Library
Access location	Centralised access location	Distributed access location
Interaction	One way communication, Loosely coupled	Two way communication, Tight coupled, Fast interaction
Search	One way search	Systematic search
Query of access	Structured text queries	Complex interaction of query, Navigation/browsing, Social filtering

Source: Devchouhary (2007)

Method

In this study, we have used a qualitative research approach, because it tells us what is important as we have focused this study on a normal situation with all its difficulties. Our focus was to construct factual description based on face-to-face knowledge of students instead of generating numerical data (Qualitative Field Research). I tried to picture it as it looked like without clarifying or simplifying it. In qualitative research, interview is often used to collect data. Interviews conducted in selected the students who have used both libraries during their

studies. A total One hundred students (55 male and 45 female students) from Panskura Banamali College Different Department I can call this sampling convenient as the Different Department has provided us the interviewee students. I have a limited time of two weeks to collect the data through interviews from Panskura Banamali College Central library. Because of this limited time, we only manage to collect the data from convenient sampling. As my study sample has represented twenty two different Department colleges' students and different levels and areas of study, we could generalise their statements (observations and

experiences) to the group outside of our sample as those findings adequately represent the existing research. Moreover, the interviewees were using both digital and manual libraries for their studies as all students from their college programme has similar experience of using both libraries due to similar environment and requirement for their study.

Data were collected with semi-structured interviews with an informal and friendly environment so that students could speak without any restraint. We have conducted face to face interviews to obtain the desired information as these interviews can give you additional information such as gesture, intonation and body language during the important point of the interviews. During the interview, I did not interrupt any of the students so that they could explain what they thought about these two different kinds of libraries. .

Result and Analysis

Interviews have been conducted in Panskura Banamali College Central library in my working office time 11a.m to 5 p.m. during 23rd July to 14th of August 2014. Access location, interaction search and query of access were the attributes of libraries being asked in the interviews plus some general and open ended questions were asked. Here we have presented the data according to the attributes mentioned above.

Access location

When talking about the problems faced about access location of digital and manual libraries students response was, in case of Digital or Electronic Library, they think that one needs to have computer or laptop to access Digital or Electronic Library but there are other restriction as well like electricity failure, internet failure some restriction from N-list/NDL such as some journals are not available and some time they need to pay to get access and some time membership is required to access, with all of these 'difficulties' still one has to have some expertise to use a Digital or Electronic Library. A female Biotechnology student said "Not all material is free of cost one has to pay for some journals and books to have access". A male student of UG 3rd years Commerce said "in digital library data is more secure because it is distributed but in traditional library it can be destroyed with fire because it is centralized". Problems faced by students in case of traditional libraries are: they get limited resources, a female student of Geography said "one has to visit library physically in all weather conditions", some books cannot be borrowed such as reference books, library card is needed to access the traditional library, have to return the book after specific time, searching a book from shelf is not easy as sometimes they are miss placed, all in all it is a time consuming process.

Interaction

When we asked questions related to easy access of resources, students explain that e-books, e-journal are always available which make it easy to access. A male student of PG History said "what you see is what you get". Huge numbers of books available on each topic in OPAC Searching but most of the students easily find their desired material online provided good internet connection, electricity and

computer. Digital or Electronic Library is limited to computer and university lab and College premises. A male student of Commerce Department said "It is easier to get a detailed study and collection of researches in traditional library as it has many reference books in the respective sections".

Search

When asked, in which library students find relevant resources in less time, they said searching is quick and less time consuming in Digital or Electronic Library but it needs some skills and expertise to search quickly as there is a lot of material available on each topic which makes it difficult to sort things out and search required material. A female student of PG Chemistry said they "search easily by using keywords and tags and easily take out irrelevant material". One can search a book from author's name or from book name in Digital or Electronic Library which make it easier to search. Another male student of PG Physics said, "Whatever you want data comes out". Finding a book is a time taking process but some students think that in traditional library all course related books are available and can be accessed. A female student of B.A. General said in traditional library "one can immediately read and use" the books.

Query of access

When we asked the students about the difference of libraries during searching, students think that Digital or Electronic Library gives them sorted out material, they just write a query and get required literature but sometimes it is not easy, they need some *searching skill* to search on Digital or Electronic Library because there is a lot of irrelevant material. A male student of PG Mathematics said about Digital or Electronic Library that "it is easy to access, acquire and sort out material". All students prefer Digital or Electronic Library as they think it is easy to access, fast to search and also have a large number of books, journals and other material related to their studies.

Discussion and Conclusions

For the usefulness of libraries we have selected the four attributes of our conceptual frame work to compare with our findings, we have discussed them with previous research also. Traditional library Physical buildings have its limitation in shape of walls and these libraries have limited number of shelves. All books in a library are present on those shelves which make this place a central hub for books and other material. In case of Digital or Electronic Library it can have a distributed access .but still student's need a computer or a laptop to get connected with Digital or Electronic Library Traditional libraries have limited number of books on each subject but Digital or Electronic Library has almost countless books on each topic. In Digital or Electronic Library search is quite an easy job, searching through keywords makes it systematic and easy to reach one's required material. in traditional libraries structured text queries are used for searching there are some manual routines/ procedures, for example if any student needs to search and issue a specific book, one needs to follow some predefined routines but in case of Digital or Electronic Library complex interaction of query, navigation, browsing and social filters are used

which helps the user to search material by using browser, enter keywords and get output of search query. Social filtering is being used as amount of data is huge which will narrow down the search material relevant to their need/desire. Students find Digital or Electronic Library as time saving, easy to use, easy to access, easy to search and get huge amount of data on it. Students have pointed out benefits of Digital or Electronic Library and traditional library which has helped us to draw a close conclusion to the reality. From the above discussion we can conclude that all students prefer Digital or Electronic Library for their study and research as it is easy to use, easy to search and easy to access even from a huge available material. Although, there are some aspect which Digital or Electronic Library cannot replace. Traditional library gives you the environment for study. One can go to traditional library and feel that intellectual atmosphere. One can hold a book in his hand and enjoy reading it. In the traditional library one can socially interact with other students.

Future Study

Further research can be carried out related to design perspective including accessibility and usability of Digital or Electronic Library.

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